

Universe without expansion and big bang

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The standard model of cosmology is confronted with a model of a universe which is curved within a five-dimensional spacetime. The redshift of the spectra of galaxies is explained by the curvature; the expansion of the universe and the big bang do not exist in this model. According to this the universe is a four-dimensional hypersphere within the five-dimensional spacetime. Its radius is calculated from the distance of standard candles.

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1. Introduction

The widely recognized big bang theory has some weaknesses and contradictions. The most serious weakness is that an eon of inflation has to be postulated in order to solve the contradiction that farthest, first galaxies are located in similar distances as the way of the light to earth which has been emitted a short time after their formation. The atoms from which they have formed must have overtaken the radiation of the big bang or in the current interpretation space must have expanded at faster than light speed. According to the theory of relativity endless energy would have been necessary for that. But infinite quantities are not accepted in physics. In order to substantiate this inflation an entirely new physics would be necessary.

The question also arises where the per se finite energy of the big bang comes from, respectively if there was a "before" or if the energy, the big bang and the whole universe emerged from "nothing". But the explanation of the emergence of "something" from "nothing" what a big bang challenges us to do, is impossible. For both notions are absolute opposites, dialectical terms. "Something" is defined as "not nothing" and vice versa.

Since 1998 the big bang theory even claims the accelerated expansion of the universe, which made it necessary to postulate the mysterious "dark energy" as explanation.

The big bang theory is so contradictory that other attempts to explain the redshift and other models of the cosmos are justified.

2. Explanation of the redshift by curvature

The articles "Relativistic addition of velocities in a five-dimensional spacetime" [1] and "Relativistic velocities and dimensions" [2] give hints on the existence of a fifth dimension of spacetime. In the here constituted hypothesis is asserted, that the three-dimensional universe is curved in the further dimension, namely first with constant curvature everywhere. Then it corresponds to a spherical surface; one can call it hypersphere. It is assumed that the redshift results from this curvature. Then the expansion of space is not needed for the explanation of the redshift; it does not exist in this model. Furthermore, is assumed that light spreads straight in this five-dimensional spacetime. By this results a bigger wavelength i.e. a redshift in the three-dimensional universe, see fig. 1.

In order to display the spreading of the light a time-axis is needed. If the three spatial dimensions are reduced to one as usual, in order to be able to display the time-axis and the w-axis of the fifth dimension too, then the concentric spherical waves around the light source become circular waves. In fig. 1 they lie on a cone shell the axis of which passes through the light source in the point A orthogonally to the x-w-plane. On this cone shell the way of the light particles from point A (with negative t-coordinate) to the observer in the coordinate origin O is part of a spiral. The orthogonal projections of the wave length on the spiral onto the x-w-plane are longer than their projections from the straight connection between A and O. Because the universe as assumed does not expand the radius of the hypersphere is constant. The circle with the arc b in fig. 1 has the same radius at all times. It is the orthogonal projection of the cylinder with the radius R and the central axis through the point M on the x-w-plane and represents the universe curved in the four-dimensional hypersphere.

Fig. 1: Projection of the straight spreading of the light of a light source in point A to the observer in the origin of the x-w-t-space; λ not true to scale

3. Derivation of formulas

Given respectively measurable are the red-shift independent luminosity distance b of relatively close galaxies and the frequencies f_0 and f from which arise the wavelengths λ_0 and λ . From this can be calculated the respective angles ζ , the radius R of the hypersphere and with that one then the distances b of far galaxies too.

The redshift is defined as
$$z = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_0} = \frac{\lambda - \lambda_0}{\lambda_0} = \frac{\lambda}{\lambda_0} - 1$$
.

It follows
$$\frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda} = \frac{1}{z+1} \quad (1)$$

As the wavefronts at the observer, at the origin, in the range of some lightyears are nearly plane respectively straight in fig. 1 and the arc there yet barely differs from the x-axis, there actually is located a right triangle in which applies in a very good approximation

$$\cos \eta = \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda} .$$

The angle between a tangent and a secant that emanates from the point of contact is always half of the centre angle of the secant, so

$$\eta = \zeta/2 \quad .$$

$$\cos \eta = \cos \frac{\zeta}{2}$$

It follows

$$\frac{\zeta}{2} = \arccos \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda}$$

and

$$\zeta = 2 \arccos \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda} \quad . \quad (2)$$

From the definition of the angle follows $R = \frac{b}{\zeta}$ (3)

4. The radius of the universe

From the redshift can be calculated with (1) and (2) the centre angle ζ to the location of a galaxy.

In the articles about galaxies in the internet, especially at Wikipedia, their distances always are stated as “hubble-distance”, that is considering the assumed expansion of space. Only in a few cases a distance independent of redshift is stated, i.e. a distance that is based on a measurement of standard candles – in most cases type Ia supernovae or sometimes cepheids – in the relevant galaxies, that is without consideration of an expansion. The hubble-distance therefore in general is larger than the redshift independent distance.

In table 1 from the redshifts and the redshift independent distance statements for four galaxies each time radius R is calculated, from which then the average is formed.

Galaxy	z	b/10 ⁶ Ly	λ_0/λ	ζ/rad	R/10 ⁶ Ly
Supernova				ζ/deg	
1. NGC 4303	0.005224	48	0.99480	0.2040	235
				11.7°	
2. NGC 5457	0.000804	21.6	0.999197	0.08017	269
SN 2011fe				4.6°	
3. NGC 1404	0.006494	65	0.99355	0.2273	286
SN2007on				13.0°	
4. NGC 4321	0.005240	53	0.99479	0.2043	259
SN 2006X				11.7°	

Table 1: Computation of the radius R of the universe in \mathbb{R}^4

As mean with scatter results $R = (263 \pm 21) \cdot 10^6 \text{Ly}$.

The maximum distance of a galaxy then is $(826 \pm 66) \cdot 10^6 \text{Ly}$.

In the standard model the self-movements of the stars, galaxies and clusters of galaxies overlap with the general expansion of the universe. In the model shown here the expansion is substituted by a general curvature. Although it is basically static there still are the self-movements which by the Doppler effect contribute to the wavelength change too. In cosmic proximity the Doppler effect may predominate the effect of curvature so that a blueshift might occur as for example at the Andromeda Galaxy with the redshift $z = -0.001001$. Therefore, the galaxy NGC 3034 was not used for the calculation of the average radius because of its relative proximity of $11.5 \cdot 10^6 \text{Ly}$ and the resulting minimal radius $R = 156 \cdot 10^6 \text{Ly}$. At the galaxy NGC 4340 on the other hand with coincidentally also $R = 156 \cdot 10^6 \text{Ly}$ the hubble distance with $40 \cdot 10^6 \text{Ly}$ is smaller than the luminosity distance of $60 \cdot 10^6 \text{Ly}$ which was determined with standard candles.

The curvature of the four-dimensional spacetime by big masses as well overlaps with the postulated general curvature. According to the present observations the universe on a large scale seems flat though. But that will be caused by the circumstance we three-dimensional beings are not experienced with – and therefore do not have imagination of a fourth spatial dimension and hence interpret indirect evidence of it – like the redshift and the addition of relativistic velocities – based on three spatial dimensions. In the outlook (paragraph 7) is predicted which future observations should contradict to that.

In paragraph 2 a constant curvature of the universe was assumed. If future observations respectively measurements should contradict to this the form of the universe could deviate from a hypersphere. But the combination of curvature in a fifth dimension and expansion is not taken into consideration in this hypothesis.

5. Further calculations

With the calculated radius R now the distances b of galaxies can be determined, that are so far away that their distances cannot be calculated from the measurements at type Ia supernovae. For example, results from the galaxy GLASS 12 discovered in 2022 with the James Webb Space Telescope with $z = 12.4$ and the hubble distance $13.6 \cdot 10^9 \text{Ly}$ from (1) and (2) the angle $\zeta = 2.992 = 171.4^\circ$. From (3) then follows $b = 787 \cdot 10^6 \text{Ly}$.

The hubble distance is 17 times bigger because of the underlying expansion.

The circumstance that x_A , the x-component of the point A for $\zeta > 90^\circ$ decreases again means that x_A is the distance in an only imagined, purely mathematical, uncurved three-dimensional space. It does not differ perceptibly from the real curved outer space in distances of some million lightyears but in larger distances the difference becomes fundamental.

As well of interest are the light path s in \mathbb{R}^4 and the coordinates of the points M and A (see fig. 1). In table 2 are listed 4 of the earliest discovered and thus closest galaxies and 4 of the just recently discovered most distant galaxies. At the first ones the calculation of s and w_A using the mean R would lead to incorrect deviations. Therefore, hereinafter for this case formulas are derived that depend of b and ζ . For distant galaxies b is not known; therefore, the respective formulas depending on R are derived.

The distance b of a far galaxy results from the definition of an angle to

$$\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{R} \cdot \zeta \quad . \quad (4)$$

If the y - and z - components of the light path are 0 like in fig. 1 then in the triangle with the corner point M and the side lengths R , R and s applies

$$s^2 = R^2 + R^2 - 2 R R \cos \zeta = 2 R^2 - 2 R^2 \cos \zeta = 2 R^2 (1 - \cos \zeta) \quad .$$

So then applies
$$\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{R} \sqrt{(2 - 2 \cos \zeta)} \quad (5)$$

For the maximum angle $\zeta = \pi$ follows $s = 2 R$ and $t = 2 R/c$.

With $R = b/\zeta$ follows
$$\mathbf{s} = \frac{\mathbf{b}}{\zeta} \sqrt{(2 - 2 \cos \zeta)} \quad (6)$$

If the light path s is specified in Lightyears and the runtime t in years the measures of s and t are equal because 1 lightyear is the distance which light passes in vacuum in 1 year.

In the lower right triangle in fig. 1 applies

$$\sin \zeta = \frac{x_A}{R} \quad ,$$

so
$$\mathbf{x}_A = \mathbf{R} \cdot \sin \zeta \quad . \quad (7)$$

With (4) follows
$$\frac{x_A}{b} = \frac{\sin \zeta}{\zeta} \quad ,$$

so
$$\mathbf{x}_A = \mathbf{b} \cdot \frac{\sin \zeta}{\zeta} \quad (8)$$

In the right triangle in fig. 1 with the vertices A and M the short cathete has the cathete length $R \cdot \cos \zeta$. The w -coordinate of A then has the absolute value

$$R - R \cdot \cos \zeta = R(1 - \cos \zeta) = \frac{b}{\zeta} (1 - \cos \zeta)$$

i.e.
$$\mathbf{w}_A = -\frac{\mathbf{b}}{\zeta} (1 - \cos \zeta) \quad . \quad (9)$$

With (4) follows
$$\mathbf{w}_A = -\mathbf{R} \cdot (1 - \cos \zeta) \quad . \quad (10)$$

In the order of the coordinates x, y, z, w, t the points A and M have the coordinates

$$\mathbf{A} \left(b \cdot \frac{\sin \zeta}{\zeta} \mid 0 \mid 0 \mid -\frac{b}{\zeta} (1 - \cos \zeta) \right)$$

or

$$\mathbf{A} (R \cdot \sin \zeta \mid 0 \mid 0 \mid -R \cdot (1 - \cos \zeta))$$

and

$$\mathbf{M} (0 \mid 0 \mid 0 \mid -263 \cdot 10^6 \text{ Lj}) \quad .$$

In the following table the data calculated with (4) till (10) are indicated.

Galaxy	Discovery	z	ζ/rad	$s/10^6 \text{ Ly}$	$x_A/10^6 \text{ Ly}$
	Discoverer	$b/10^6 \text{ Ly}$	ζ/deg	$t/10^6 \text{ a}$	$w_A/10^6 \text{ Ly}$
1. NGC 4303	1779	0.005224	0.2040	47.9	47,7
	B. Oriani	48	11.7°	47.9	-4,88
2. NGC 5457	1781	0.000804	0.08017	21.59	21,58
	P. Méchain	21.6	4.6°	21.59	-0,865
3. NGC 1404	1837	0.006498	0.2273	64.9	64,4
	J. Herschel	65	13.0°	64.9	-7,36
4. NGC 4321	1781	0.005240	0.2043	52.9	52,6
	P. Méchain	53	11.7°	52.9	-5,39
5. IOK-1	2006	6.96	2.890	522	65,5
	M. Iye	760	166°	522	-518
6. UDFy-	2009	8.55	2.931	523	55,0
38135539	Hubble-Tele.	771	168°	523	-520
7. GLASS-z12	2022	12.4	2.992	524.5	39,2
	J.-Webb-Tele.	787	171.4°	524.5	-523,0
8. JADES-GS-	2024	14	3.010	524.9	34,5
z14-0	J.-Webb-Tele.	792	172.5°	524.9	-523,8

Table 2: Centre angles, distances and coordinates of some of the closest and most distant galaxies

6. Advantages of the curvature hypothesis over the big bang theory

The handicaps of the big bang theory, the standard model of cosmology, stated in the introduction do not exist in the curvature hypothesis.

As the curvature hypothesis describes a basic static cosmos without expansion there is no beginning and no end in time. Thus misses the intellectual problem having to explain the existence of the universe in contrast to its non-existence. The “horror vacui” is avoided. For the notions existence and non-existence are only applicable to parts of the cosmos, not to the entirety. Only the parts arise and disappear and thereby are definable as notions and by that depictable i.e. existent. Expressed the other way round there is no difference between existence and non-existence for the cosmos. This idea had already the antique Greek philosopher Parmenides of Elea (515 – 470 B. C.). The idea of Heraklit of Ephesus (535 – 470 B. C.) that in the world only an eternal change (panta rhei) takes place also implies that there was no emergence from nothing and thus is an intellectual tradition for the curvature hypothesis.

The postulated “inflation” of the universe with more than light speed and infinite energy – actually rejected physical phenomena – also is omitted in the curvature hypothesis.

Together with the expansion also disappears the accelerated expansion and thus the postulate of a “dark energy”. It can be explained by a stronger curvature.

As well unnecessary are explanations for the observation that the galaxies and galaxy clusters do not expand together with space and that no gravitational time effects occur by the expansion.

7. Summary and outlook

By the concept of a five-dimensional spacetime [1], [2], [3], [4] the redshift of the galaxies can be explained more problem-free than by the big bang theory.

Based on the curvature hypothesis can be predicted that at further progress in space-based telescope technology finally galaxies will be observable that are located at the opposite point of the hypersphere of universe. At observations in any directions the same formations of galaxies – just turned – must appear.

An additional prediction is that before this region does not exist a dark zone, for this scenario is based on the expansion or compression in the big bang theory. Consequently can be predicted that the therefrom resulting expected limits of the redshift of $z = 30$ for first stars and $z = 1100$ for the beginning of the dark age (background radiation $z = 1089$) shall be exceeded. The limit of $z = 20$ for the end of the dark age from which results a maximum angle of $\zeta = 3.05 = 175^\circ$ nearly is already reached. At measurements of $z > 20$ the big bang theory would start to waver.

In the curvature hypothesis from (2) follows for the maximum angle $\zeta = \pi$

$$\pi = 2 \arccos \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda}$$

then $\frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda} = 0$

and with (1) $\frac{1}{z+1} = 0$

which becomes true only for z towards infinity. Therefore, very big redshifts are to be expected which at most will reach a metrological limit in the spectroscope.

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